

BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNI QO'LLAB QUVVATLASHNING DAVLAT VA NODAVLAT SHAKLLARI

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KEYWORDS

Business, budget, license,
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ABSTRACT

Foreign experience of state support for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, improvement of the entrepreneurship support system, additional measures to further improve the business environment. Economic development and poverty reduction.

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KALIT SO'ZLAR:

Biznes, byudjet, litsenziya, moliyaviy resurs, tadbirkorlik

ANNOTATSIYA

Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishni davlat tomonidan qo'llab-qo'vatlashning xorij tajribasi, tadbirkorlikni qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimini takomillashtirish, ishbilarmonlik muhitini yanada yaxshilash bo'yicha qo'shimcha chora tadbirlar. Iqtisodiy taraqqiyot va kambag'alchilikni qisqartirish.

Bozor munosabatlari sharoitida iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning asosiy omillaridan biri kichik biznes va tadbirkorlik faolyatini rivojlantirishdir.

Biznes yuritish shart-sharoitlarni yanada yaxshilash, tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishga oid islohotlarni izchil davom ettirish, tadbirkorlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarini kengaytirish, ularni zarur moliyaviy va infratuzilmaviy resurslar bilan ta'minlash maqsadida 2021-yil 1-maydan boshlab tadbirkorlik sub'ektlarni davlat tomonida qo'llab-quvvatlash choralari ko'rilmogda.

Biznes va tadbirkorlik bu tadbirkorlik faolyatidan yoki boshqacha qilib aytganda kishilarni foyda olishga qaratilgan faolyatdir.

Bu faolyatni shakllantirish uchun ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, huquqiy va boshqa muayyan sharoitlar yaratilishi kerak. Iqtisodiy sharoitlarga masalan tovarga bo'lgan talab va taklif, xaridor sotib olish uchun tova turlarini mavjudligi, xaridor sotib olish uchun zarur pul hajmini mavjudligi, ishchi kuchlarini ortiqchalik va yetishmovchilik kiradi. Bu ishlar bilan bozor infratuzulmasini tashkil etgan turli tashkilotlar shug'ullanadi. Tadbirkorlar esa tashkilotlar bilan aloqa o'rnatib tijorat operatsiyalarini amalga oshiradi.

Biznesni va tadbirkorlikni qo'llab quvvatlashning davlat va nodavlat shakllari bu to'rt yo'nalishda ya'ni

- Sanoat korxonalarini xodimlarini rag'batlantirib ularni ko'proq marketing tadqiqotlarini olib borishga jalb qilish orqali yangi innovatsion g'oyalarini ishlab chiqishga yo'naltirish

- Sanoat korxonalarida ishlayotgan yosh xodimlar tomonidan yaratilayotgan innovatsion loyihalarni amalyotda qo'llashdan oldin korxonada hududiga tegishli joylarda sinov maydonchalarini tashkil etishni yo'lga qo'yish

- Kichik biznes vakillari va xususiy tadbirkorlar uchun kreditlar va ular uchun zarur resurslardan foydalanish imkoniyatini kengaytirish va yaratilayotgan innovatsion loyihalarni kreditlash tizimini yaratish

- Viloyatlarning chekka tumanlarida ishlab chiqarishda eng muhim omil bo'lgan elektr energiyasi, tabiiy gaz, ichimlik suvi va shu kabi kommunal xizmatlar uzluksizligini ta'minlash bilan bog'liq bo'lgan muammolarni hal etishdir.

Shu bilan biznes fondning asosiy vazifalari bu kichik va o'rta tadbirkorlik tuzulmalariga respublika tovar bozozrlarini to'ldirish, yangi ish o'rinlarini barpo etish uchun molyaviy yordam ko'rsatishdir. Biznesning asosini, shuningdek uning kichik ko'rinishlarini molyaviy sarmoyalar va molyaviy zaxiralar tashkil qiladi. Xo'jalik yurutuvchi sub'yektning molyaviy zaxiralarini uning ixtiyorida bo'lgan pul vositalari tashkil qiladi.

Hozirgi vaqtda yurtimizda kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni asosan savdo-sotiq, xizmati va aloqa sohasida, qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini qayta ishlash bo'yicha ko'proq rivoj topmoqda.

Jahon iqtisodiyoti globallasuvi va raqobat muhiti kuchayib borish, mahsulotlar hayotiylik davri keskin qisqarish, bozor konyukturasi va istimolchilar ehtiyojlari tez o'zgarishi jarayonlari bugungi kunda har bir xo'jalik yurutuvchi sebyektdan raqobatbardosh mahsulotlar ishlab chiqishning tashkiliy iqtisodiy mexanizmlarini ishlab chiqishni hayotiy zaruratga aylantirmoqda. Bu esa ularning inavatsion faolyatini rivojlantirish va samarali boshqarishni talab etmoqda. Shu bilan birga biz zamonaviy, ilg'or va tejamkor texnologiyalardan foydalanishga hamda tovarlarning yuqori sifat va iste'mol xususiatlarini taminlashga xizmat qiladigan texnika va texnologiyalarni yaratish tizimini joriy etsak, bu sohaga yoshlarni jalb qilsak bu sohaga yoshlarni jalb qilgan holda aholimizning ichki ehtiyojlarini taminlash bilan birga eksportga xizmat qiladigan raqobatbardosh, sifatli mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarishni yanada kuchaytirishga erishishimiz mumkin. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining farmoni bilan tashkil etilgan kichik va o'rta biznes rivojlantirishga ko'maklashish jamg'armasi eng muhim molyaviy vosita hisoblanadi.

Xulosa: Har bir mamlakatning kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishni davlat tomonidan qo'llab-qo'vatlash keng ko'lamda olib borilayotgan sohalarda ko'rish mumkin. Biznes va tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishga oid islohatlarni izchil davom ettirish, tadbirkorlikni qo'llab-quvatlashni molyalashtirish zarur.

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